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THE AMERICAN PEDIATRIC SOCIETY'S COLLECTIVE INVESTIGATION ON INFANTILE SCURVY IN NORTH AMERICA.*

The subject of infantile scurvy has so recently come into prominence, and still presents so many mooted questions, especially regarding its etiology, that it was the decision of the American Pediatric Society a year ago to undertake a collective investigation of the matter, based upon the cases occurring in America. This seemed particularly needed, as no other such study upon a large number of cases has yet been made in any country.

The committee, which is now making its report, was accordingly appointed. It has been diligently at work during nearly a year, and has used every means in its power to reach reports of cases of the disease. A list as accurate as possible was prepared of all the medical journals of North America, and a notice of the proposed investigation was sent to each, inviting correspondence on the part of all readers. Letters were sent to the secretaries of the county societies in a large number of the States of the Union requesting that notice be given at the meetings. Letters were also addressed to the professors of diseases of children in all the regular medical colleges of the United States. The "Index Medicus" was searched for the names of those who had published reports of cases, and letters were addressed to all of them, as indeed to all physicians of whom even the rumor had come of probable cases under their charge. Circulars were printed containing questions to be answered, and were sent to all the members of the American Pediatric Society, to all physicians applying for them, and finally wherever there seemed any chance of getting a response.

The questions contained in the circular requested information on the following points: Whether the case was seen in hospital

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or private practice; the race, sex, and age; the hygienic surroundings, family history, and previous illnesses; full details of feeding from birth, and the influence which the food appeared to have had upon the development of the disease; the symptoms in detail, with special reference to pain and its location, apparent paralysis or inability to move, swellings, fractures, hemorrhages, the condition of the gums, the presence of fever, the condition of the urine and bowels, the presence of anæmia or mal-nutrition and of rickets or any other complicating diseases, and the character of the first symptom to develop; the treatment in detail, with duration of illness, and the time before decided improvement was discovered; the direct cause of death in fatal cases, and the *post-mortem* findings; and finally, whether the case had been published previously.

The committee has been surprised and pleased at the large number of replies received. There are other cases of which it has knowledge of which no reports could be obtained, and undoubtedly many more whose existence was not discovered. But in all the committee has collected 379 cases seen by 138 observers. Some of the cases are very incompletely reported, but in the majority of instances the answers are for the most part satisfactory. No cases needed to be excluded as instances of mistaken diagnosis, although a very few were somewhat doubtful.

The topics covered by the questions can best be taken up for the most part seriatim, stating merely what the reports state, without vouching for the correctness of opinions.

RACE.—The race to which the subjects of the disease belong is stated in 372 cases. It is not given with definiteness sufficiently often to allow of an analysis further than to say that there were 367 white, 4 black, and 1 Chinese.

SEX.—Sex shows out of 372 cases, 189 male, *i.e.*, 51 per cent.; and 183 female, *i.e.*, 49 per cent.; a difference not decided enough to indicate that sex is an etiological factor. In the remaining cases the sex is not mentioned.

AGE.—Age is a very important matter. Although strictly speaking, the age of the cases of infantile scurvy should be limited to those under two years, the committee has ventured to include a few in children slightly or decidedly older than this; since the etiology and symptoms are not different in any respect. Question IV. on the circular reads: "Age when seen

with Scurvy," while XIV. reads: "Duration of Illness Before Treatment was Commenced." By combining the answers to these two questions, the age at which the illness developed could be determined in most instances. Reliable information was given in 359 cases; in the remaining number the age was unknown or was not stated. The accompanying tabular arrangement shows the number of cases developing at different ages:

AGE WHEN SCURVY DEVELOPED.					
AGE.	NO. OF CASES.	PER-CENTAGE.	AGE.	NO. OF CASES.	PER-CENTAGE.
3 weeks,	1	.27	16 months,	7	1.70
1½ months,	1	.27	17 "	6	1.67
2 "	3	.83	18 "	7	1.70
3 "	2	.55	19 "	4	1.11
4 "	9	2.50	20 "	2	.55
5 "	5	1.40	22 "	1	.27
6 "	13	3.62	23 "	1	.27
7 "	33	9.19	2 years,	2	.55
8 "	41	11.42	2 years, 3 mo.	1	.27
9 "	47	13.09	2 " 6 "	1	.27
10 "	51	14.20	2 " 7 "	1	.27
11 "	26	7.24	2 " 8 "	1	.27
12 "	25	7.00	3 " 6 "	1	.27
13 "	25	7.00	4 " 2 "	1	.27
14 "	22	6.12	6 "	1	.27
15 "	17	4.73	9 "	1	.27

It will be seen that the disease is most apt to develop between the ages of seven and fourteen months, inclusive. The youngest case was that reported by Dr. A. Matheson of Neillsville, Wis. This was a child of four weeks who had already been ill five days when first seen. The child was fed at the breast. Its hygienic surroundings were poor. The disease exhibited perfectly typical symptoms and ended fatally.

The oldest child, reported by Dr. J. H. Fruitnight, was one of nine years, and was also a typical case, rapidly recovering under dietetic treatment. The cause appeared to be improper diet.

SOCIAL POSITION.—Of 379 cases it is interesting to note that 83 per cent. occurred in private practice, and only 17 per cent. in hospital practice. Although no absolute class distinctions can be based on these figures, yet they point very positively to the greater tendency of the disease to occur among the rich or the well-to-do. This tendency is still further illustrated by the statements of the writers regarding the *hygienic surroundings* of

the cases. In 303 cases these are described as good, and often the statement is volunteered that they were of the very best. In 5 they were doubtful, and in only 40 are they described as bad. The figures of the report would therefore seem to indicate that the influence of bad hygienic conditions upon the etiology of the disease is extremely limited.

PREVIOUS HEALTH.—Out of 285 cases suitable for study, it is distinctly stated in 167 that the previous health had been good. In 118 the child had suffered from various diseased conditions which may be enumerated as follows:

Bronchitis, 5; chickenpox, 1; constipation, 1; convulsions, 3; cretinism, 1; diarrhœal conditions, 45; eczema, 1; furunculosis, 1; indigestion, 22; influenza, 6; malaria, 1; measles, 7; pneumonia, 5; rheumatism, 1; scurvy (previous attack), 1; scrofulous diathesis, 1; typhoid fever, 1; whooping cough, 2.

It is evident that the occurrence of most of these diseases can only be considered as accidental. There is a striking preponderance of instances of digestive disturbance. This probably is an indication that the faulty diet which occasioned the scurvy produced the indigestion also. It is no proof that the digestive disease itself bore any etiological relation to the constitutional affection. This is clearly the view of the correspondents, for, in answer to the question of the circular, a belief in any other cause than diet is expressed in only 24 instances.

Rickets, anæmia, and mal-nutrition are not mentioned in the foregoing list. They will be referred to later.

Attention may be called to the instance of a second attack of scurvy reported by Dr. L. E. Holt. The child was eighteen months of age at the time of the second attack, the previous one having developed four months before. The first attack followed the use of Mellin's food and sterilized milk. Recovery followed in a week upon a diet of sterilized milk and beef juice, no fruit juice being given. The second attack followed the use of Reed & Carnrick's soluble food. The patient in this attack was in a wretched condition and died in eight days.

The case of scurvy developing in a cretin, reported by Dr. A. Caillé is also interesting. The child was a typical cretin of fourteen months. Scurvy followed the use of condensed milk. Recovery was very prompt under the administration of sterilized milk, fruit juice and cereals.

FAMILY HISTORY.—This too appears to exert little or no influ-

ence. In 129 cases the family history is stated to have been good, and in 97 it is negative. In 74 the following diseases are mentioned in the family:

Alcoholism, 2; anæmia, 2; asthma, 1; carcinoma, 1; caries of spine, 1; diarrhœa, 1; eczema, 1; gout, 2; neurotic tendency, 6; paresis, 1; pneumonia, 1; rheumatism, 16; sciatica, 1; scurvy, 1; syphilis, 7; tuberculosis, 29; uricacidæmia, 1.

DIET.—The most important etiological factor, according to general opinion, is a dietetic one. Consequently, the committee has paid particular attention to this point. When correspondents did not make the matter quite clear in their answers, personal letters were addressed to them, asking for further information. A large number of such letters have been written, and replies received in most instances. Full details were asked regarding diet from birth onward, and the question of food used at the time the scurvy developed, or so shortly before that it might seem to be associated with it, was particularly emphasized. The question was also asked, whether in the opinion of each correspondent there was reason to believe that the disease depended on the nature of the food used. An affirmative answer was received in 275 cases; negative, and the disease attributed to other causes, in 24. The committee is not in a position to judge of the correctness of this view, nor can it claim that the disease *did* arise in any instance as the result of the diet employed. It would make merely the following statements of the food employed at or shortly before the symptoms of scurvy were observed, according to the reporters' replies.

Any accurate percentage analysis of the report is impossible, both because the correspondents have not always stated the exact nature of the food, and because in very many instances more than one form of food was given. Perhaps the following summary of some of the main divisions may be of value, remembering, however, that cases are repeatedly counted twice; *e.g.*, one case may be counted in the condensed milk class and again in the sterilized milk division.

FOOD USED AT OR SHORTLY BEFORE SCURVY DEVELOPED.

Number of cases in which the character of the food is specified, 356.

Food given as follows:

Breast Milk.—Alone, 10; with raw milk and amylaceæ, 1; with sterilized milk and amylaceæ, 1; total, 12.

Raw Milk.—Alone, 4; with breast milk and amylaceæ, 1; total, 5.

Milk (nothing said about heating).—Alone, 8; peptonized, 4; with amylaceæ, 4; total, 16.

Sterilized Milk.—Alone, 68; with proprietary foods, 21; with amylaceæ, 8; peptonized, 10; total, 107.

Pasteurized Milk.—Alone, 16; with proprietary foods, 2; with amylaceæ, 1; peptonized, 1; total, 20.

Peptonized Milk.—Nothing further stated, 3; sterilized, 8; pasteurized, 1; with proprietary foods, 1; with amylaceæ, 1; total, 14.

Amylaceous Food (not proprietary).—Alone, 6; with breast milk, 3; with milk, 5; with sterilized milk, 8; with pasteurized milk, 1; with peptonized milk, 1; total, 24. (9 of these were oat meal).

Table Food.—Nothing else mentioned, 11; with condensed milk, 1; total, 12.

Mellin's Food.—Nothing further stated, 42; with condensed milk, 22; with sterilized milk, 16; with pasteurized milk, 2; with other proprietary food, 1; total, 83.

Malted Milk.—Nothing further stated, 44; with cream, 1; with amylaceæ, 1; with other proprietary foods, 2; total, 48.

Condensed Milk.—Alone, 32; with milk, 1; with cream, 1; with other proprietary foods, 3; with table food, 1; total, 38.

Reed & Carnrick's Soluble Food.—13.

Imperial Granum.—6.

Liebig's Food.—Alone, 1; with condensed milk, 1; total, 2.

Lactated Food.—Alone, 3; with condensed milk, 1; total, 4.

Nestle's Food.—Alone, 1; with sterilized peptonized milk, 1; total, 2.

Among other articles of diet mentioned by correspondents, each in one instance, are: Gardner's food, Robinson's barley, Ridge's food, Brush's food, animal broths, Bartlett's pepsinated food, Lactopræparata with Malted milk.

There are a number of instances in which the writers mention "proprietary foods" without further designation. In all 214 cases (60 per cent.) were fed on proprietary foods.

The effect of dietetic treatment has such an important bearing upon the etiological influence of diet that the whole matter will be discussed more fully under Treatment.

SYMPTOMS.—The symptoms in infantile scurvy are so typical and well known that they would appear to need little further

study. Nevertheless, the attention which has been directed to them by the questions of the circular has not been without fruit.

FIRST SYMPTOM TO DEVELOP AND ORDER AND TIME OF OTHER SYMPTOMS.—In response to this question the answers have not been altogether satisfactory. Undoubtedly in a large number such early symptoms as anæmia and mal-nutrition were overlooked or were not included by the readers as symptoms of the disease. Then in a large number, perhaps the majority of cases, answers have not made it quite clear whether the correspondent intended that a certain number of symptoms developed in the order in which the names are written, or whether they all were noticed at one time. Presuming that the first is the writer's intention, we make the following statement of the first symptom seen, basing this on 327 cases. The order of symptoms is too complicated and too uncertain to warrant a statistical arrangement.

FIRST SYMPTOMS SEEN.—Pain and tenderness, 145; affection of gums, 42; interference with motion, 36; anæmia, 27; cutaneous hemorrhages, 22; swellings, 16; restlessness, 6; anorexia, 5; debility, 5; diarrhœa, 5; constipation, 2; hemorrhage from nose, 1; hemorrhage from mouth, 1; hemorrhage from rectum, 1; hæmaturia, 3; "hæmatoma of tongue," 1; irritability, 3; vomiting, 1; fever, 1; opisthotonos, 1; sweating, 1.

PAIN ON MOTION OR HANDLING.—Pain is clearly a very prominent symptom of the disease. Generally it is evident only when the child is moved, or tries to move itself. Sometimes it is so intense that the approach of any one to the bedside is sufficient to cause the child to scream out through fear of being touched. Pain is reported present in 314 instances. In most of the remaining, no answer was made, and it is probable that the symptom could not have been a prominent one. The locality of the pain in the cases where there were accurate details was as follows:

Legs, 120; legs and arms, 25; legs and one arm, 11; legs and body, 4; one leg, 13; one leg and one arm, 1; one arm, 1; back, 1; back and legs, 1; back and leg, 1; back and thighs, 1; thighs, 1; hips and thigh, 1; one thigh, 2; one hip, 2; knees, 1; knees and ankles, 2; knees, ankles and shoulders, 1; knees, ankles and wrists, 2; knees and arms, 1; one knee, 1; one ankle, 1; ankles, 1; ankles and feet, 1; ankles and elbows, 1; elbow, 1.

PAIN WHEN AT REST.—In 91 cases pain seems to have been present, even when the child was still; while in 134 it is definitely stated as absent under this condition.

INTERFERENCE WITH MOTION.—The symptom variously described as *paralysis*, *pseudo-paralysis* and *disability* or *unwillingness to move* is reported frequently. It probably depends in every instance upon pain, since there is no evidence that actual paralysis occurs in the disease. In 319 cases interference with motion of this nature existed.

Rigidity is described as present in 96 cases and absent in 106. It is due to pain in most instances, but perhaps in others may have been occasioned or increased by the presence of swelling.

The parts of the body in which motion has been interfered with in any way in the cases reported, and the locality mentioned in detail, may be enumerated as follows:

Legs, 159; legs and arms, 55; legs and one arm, 14; legs and one hand, 2; one arm, 3; legs and thighs, 1; thighs, 3; one leg and one arm, 1; one leg, 27; one thigh, 2; hips, 1; one hip, 2; one hip and thigh, 1; one hip and knee, 3; hip, leg and shoulder, 1; hip, elbow and shoulder, 1; one knee, 4; one ankle, 2; ankles, knees, hand and wrist, 1.

POSITION OF THE LIMBS.—To a question regarding the position of the limbs, about which Barlowe speaks so definitely, there have been replies in 205 cases. In 17 of these the position was normal. In the balance we find the position of the limbs as follows:

Flexed, 152; extended, 23; flexed and abducted, 1; flexed and adducted, 1; flexed and everted, 1; abducted, 1; everted, 3; everted and extended, 2; toes extended, 1; feet extended, 3.

WEAKNESS OF THE BACK.—The occurrence of weakness of the back, a symptom which Barlowe says is marked, is mentioned as present in 97 of the cases reported to the committee and as absent in 108. In the remaining nothing is said of it.

DEPRESSION OF THE STERNUM.—This condition is likewise emphasized by Barlowe as being sometimes striking and characteristic. It is mentioned in 34 cases, but said to be absent in 170 others. It is not certain in the cases of the report how frequently the condition had developed acutely as a result of scurvy and how often it had already been produced by a previously existing rachitis.

SWELLINGS.—The effort has been made by analyzing the cases collected to determine the position of local swellings, whether these were situated in the joints or the shafts of the limbs, in the soft tissues or in the bones, and whether any redness was present. The answers are not clear in every in-

stance, and are frequently somewhat contradictory, partly, perhaps, from failure of the observer to understand the question, and partly from lack of careful discrimination between sub-periosteal and other effusions, and between effusion into a joint and that about it. The great irregularity also of the distribution of the swelling renders an accurate tabular arrangement too complicated. Remembering that in many cases more than one part of the body was involved and that the figures given do not mean that only the portion mentioned is affected in these cases, the following division may be made:

Joints (or probably oftener about joints) involved in 165 cases. Location given in 101; *viz.*:

Knees, 73; ankles, 28; wrists, 12; hand, 1; elbow, 3; shoulder, 5; hip, 6.

Shafts of limbs involved in 179 cases. Location given in 123; *viz.*:

Thighs, 59; legs (below knee), 61; "legs" (not further stated), 11; forearm, 5; upper arm, 4; "arm," 5; ribs, 1; scapula, 1; ilium, 1.

The gross results of the answers regarding the tissues in which the swelling occurred give:

Swelling in soft tissues, 97.

Swelling, sub-periosteal, 114.

Swelling in both situations, 16.

In 69 cases the swollen parts were reddened also. It is stated that there was no redness in 121. A more general swelling, to be classified rather as œdema, is described in 68 cases and stated to be absent in 98.

In regard to the swelling or protrusion of one or both eyes which has been described by writers, the symptom is said to have been absent in 110 cases and is reported present in 49. In 9 of these swelling only is mentioned, in 18 protrusion only, and in 22 both are referred to.

GUMS.—The condition of the gums and mouth is one of extreme interest. In 16 cases it is distinctly stated that the gums were entirely unaffected, while in 313 they were diseased. The degree of involvement varies from slight swelling to great sponginess and even ulceration. The degree and form of the affection in the cases suitable for study may be seen in the following table:

Swelling, absent, 14; present, 293.

Sponginess, absent, 27; present, 249.

Discoloration, absent, 23; present, 259.

Bleeding, absent, 64; present, 188.

Ulceration, absent, 101; present, 91.

The relation of the affection of the gums to the presence of teeth is of much interest. In nearly all the cases of scurvy in this report teeth were present, but what influence this has is not quite clear, since experience teaches that curiously it is usually the gums of the upper jaw which are most affected, although the lower teeth naturally are the first cut. Statistics on the portion of the gums involved were not furnished sufficiently to allow of conclusions; but regarding the teeth it is to be noted that of 359 cases suitable for comparison, teeth had already appeared in 314 instances, *i.e.*, 87.5 per cent.; while in only 45 cases, *i.e.*, 12.5 per cent., were there no teeth. In studying more carefully these 45 cases of scurvy without teeth, we may make the following analysis:

No teeth; gums normal, 21 cases.

No teeth; gums affected, 24 cases.

The conditions present in the latter group were as follows:

Swelling, 19 cases; sponginess, 14 cases; bleeding, 5 cases; discoloration, 17 cases; ulceration, 4 cases.

This is a proof that affection of the gums may occur equally well when there are no teeth as when teeth have developed. The fact that in the great majority of cases of infantile scurvy the presence of teeth and the affection of the gums is associated, depends merely on the fact that the disease generally develops at an age when teeth naturally have been cut.

CUTANEOUS HEMORRHAGES.—These have occurred with frequency in the cases reported. Accurate data are given in 353 cases. Of these, cutaneous hemorrhage is reported present in 182 and absent in 171. There is much doubt about the accuracy of the writers in their classification of the hemorrhages according to size, and the proper use by them of the descriptive names employed, inasmuch as the question on this point did not specify clearly. In 99 instances the presence of "ecchymoses" is mentioned. In 83 "purpuric eruption" is reported and in 37 "petechiæ." In 13 the nature of the lesion is not specified.

HEMORRHAGE FROM MUCOUS MEMBRANES.—Data are available in 361 cases. Of these there were no hemorrhages from any mucous membrane in 196, while in 164 they occurred. In 93 cases there was hemorrhage from the mouth. This includes the

cases where bleeding from the gums is described by writers. In 33 cases there was bleeding from the nose; in 2 from the stomach, and in 37 from the bowels. Cases of hæmaturia are not included here, and will be referred to later.

FRACTURES.—Fractures in infantile scurvy are usually separations of the epiphyses merely. Even this would seem to be rare, for fracture of any kind is mentioned in only 9 of our cases. In 342 it is distinctly stated to have been absent, and in the remaining the question is not answered.

FEVER.—Probably in the majority of the cases of the disease upon which this report is based no temperature record has been made. In 93 cases it is stated that there was no fever; in 182 it was present and in the remaining no answer is given. In the cases where present it is described as slight in 116 instances, moderate in 23, high in 8, and irregular in 6. Clearly, fever is not a prominent symptom of the disease, and probably often, when present, depends on accidental causes.

BOWEL MOVEMENTS.—The following conditions are mentioned:

Bowels regular, 74.

Bowels irregular, 15.

Constipation, 126.

Diarrhœa, 65.

Bloody diarrhœa, 12.

URINE.—Judging from the number of instances in which no answers have been returned, no examination of the urine has been made in most of the cases. It is reported as examined for albumin in 163 cases; in 33 of these albuminuria is reported and in 130 it was absent. Tube casts were present in 13 instances, absent in 13, and no observation reported in the others.

Properly speaking the occurrence of hæmaturia should be discussed under the title of hemorrhage. It is mentioned as present in 22 cases only. Of other abnormal conditions of the urine the following may be mentioned: Urine very acid, 1; urine scanty, 9; urine suppressed, 1; urine increased in quantity, 3; glycosuria, 1; hæmoglobinuria, 1; pus (from cystitis), 1; phosphates increased, 1; chlorides increased, 1.

ANÆMIA; MAL-NUTRITION.—These conditions, already referred to as often the earliest symptoms of infantile scurvy, may have been the first evidences of the disease in many of the cases on which this report is based. In other cases they must be regarded as complicating affections only. Answers are not full enough to allow of satisfactory conclusions on this point.

Anæmia is said to have been present in 254 cases, as follows:
Anæmia present (without specifying degree), 47.

Anæmia slight, 66.

Anæmia moderate, 32.

Anæmia marked, 109.

Blood examinations were made in 15 cases and the conditions noted as follows: The percentage of hæmoglobin was much reduced in all the cases, 8 in number, in which an examination was made, some being as low as 35 per cent. Of the 7 cases in which the red blood corpuscles were counted, all showed a reduction except 2. In these 2 the number was normal or nearly so, but the hæmoglobin was 50 and 35 per cent., respectively. Leucocytosis was present in 5 cases. Poikilocytosis in 2. In only one instance was there a differential count of the leucocytes made.

Of 217 cases in which the question is answered, *emaciation* is recorded in 167 and is said to have been absent in 50.

Mal-nutrition was observed in 178 cases out of 216, in which replies were made as follows:

Mal-nutrition present (without specifying degree), 108; slight, 20; moderate, 7; marked, 43.

RICKETS.—Infantile scurvy has so often been described as "scurvy rickets" and "acute rickets," that the investigation of the actual relationship of the two diseases was one of the matters to which the committee directed especial attention. The question upon the circular reads as follows: (a) "Any symptoms of rickets present? (b) Slight or well marked? (c) What relation in time of development did they bear to the scurvy?" Satisfactory answers were received in 340 cases; in 152 of these (45 per cent.), there were symptoms of rickets present, slight in 72, marked in 64, and the degree not mentioned in 16. In the remaining cases (55 per cent.), rickets is definitely stated to have been absent. With regard to the relation in time of development, it is stated in 50 cases that the rickets was first present; in 14 that it developed with the scurvy, and in 2 after it. There does not seem to be evidence as far as this investigation teaches that the association of rickets and scurvy is at all intimate. Very possibly the same defect in diet which produced the one produced the other also, but the rapid recovery under treatment which the scurvy underwent did not apply to the rickets. This seems to indicate only accidental association of the two diseases; certainly not any causal relation between them.

OTHER COMPLICATING CONDITIONS.—A variety of affections are mentioned complicating scurvy in a number of cases, as follows:

Bronchitis, 5; cretinism, 1; enlargement of inguinal glands, 1; "cerebral symptoms," 1; convulsions, 1; pneumonia, 2; boils, 1; irritability, 1; vomiting, 4; eczema, 2; enuresis, 1; sweating of the head, 1; tympanites, 1; caput medusæ, 1; diaphoresis, 1; pertussis, 2; insomnia, 1; anorexia, 2; post nasal discharge, 1; measles, 1; restlessness, 1; phimosis, 1; indigestion, 2; laryngismus stridulus, 1; cystitis, 1.

DIAGNOSIS.—The study of diagnosis has been only incidental, based upon the mistakes made before the disease was recognized in certain cases. The only disease for which infantile scurvy was repeatedly taken appears to have been rheumatism. In several instances the affection of the legs was supposed to be due to sarcoma. The apparent paralytic condition has also been the cause of error in some instances.

DURATION OF ILLNESS AND PROGNOSIS.—The disease is essentially chronic; its course terminating only on the institution of proper treatment. This seems to be proved by the answers contained in the circulars. To the question concerning the *duration of the disease before the case came under observation*, replies were received in 306 cases, of which the following analysis may be made:

DURATION OF DISEASE BEFORE TREATMENT WAS COMMENCED.

DAYS.	CASES.	WEEKS.	CASES.	MONTHS.	CASES.
2	3	1	15	1	18
3	3	2	33	2	42
5	2	3	58	3	31
8	1	4	22	4	14
9	1	5	8	5	4
10	9	6	29	6	7
24	1	7	6	7	2
		8	1	10	1
		10	3	12	1
				2½ yrs.	1

Intensely interesting in this connection are the replies to the next two questions: First, *Duration of illness after treatment was commenced*, and second, *Duration of treatment before marked improvement was noticed*. To the first question replies concerning 308 cases were received. Of course those fatal during the attack of scurvy are not included here nor those which passed from observation.

Still more striking are the answers to the second question, as

to the time when marked improvement was first noticed. There are 311 cases suitable for study in this category, excluding fatal cases and those passing from observation as before. The replies are often astonishing. Nothing is more striking than the speed with which these reports show a grave constitutional disease disappearing under proper treatment. There is certainly no disease for which a more specific treatment can be said to exist. The replies to the last two questions may be conveniently stated in the following tables:

DURATION OF TREATMENT BEFORE MARKED IMPROVEMENT WAS NOTICED.

DAYS.	CASES.	WEEKS.	CASES.	MONTHS.	CASES.
1	19	1	47	1	6
2	58	2	27	2	4
3	46	3	8	3	4
4	26	4	1		
5	19	5	1		
6	1	6	1		
7	2				
8	2				
9	1				
10	7				
12	2				

Reported as prompt recovery, 13; at once, 15; immediate, 1.

DURATION OF TREATMENT BEFORE RECOVERY WAS COMPLETE.

DAYS.	CASES.	WEEKS.	CASES.	MONTHS.	CASES.
1	6	1	48	1	28
2	5	2	54	2	14
3	14	3	36	3	5
4	8	4	14	4	2
5	5	5	6	5	1
6	1	6	14	6	2
8	2	7	1	7	1
10	17			8	1
12	3			9	1
13	3				
15	2				
16	1				

Reported as immediate, 4; almost immediate, 9.

TREATMENT.—Not so much could be learned of the value of treatment as could be desired on account of the fact that in nearly all cases we have a combination of diet and of medicinal measures, including the use of fruit juices, and it is impossible to determine absolutely which was the active curative agent.

Taking the cases in which treatment was effectual and which are suitable for study, the results may be stated as follows:

- I. Cases recovering under treatment with drugs only (no change in diet), - - - - - 0
- II. Cases recovering under the use of fruit juice alone (no change in diet), - - - - - 3
- III. Cases recovering under the use of beef juice alone (no other change in diet), - - - - - 2
- IV. Cases recovering under the use of beef juice and fruit juice combined, with or without drugs (no change in diet), - - - - - 6
- V. Cases recovering under the combined effect of change of diet, often including beef juice, and the employment of fruit juice, with or without drugs, - - - 257
- VI. Cases recovering under change of diet, often including beef juice, and use of drugs (no fruit juice). - 20
- VII. Cases recovering under change of diet alone, often including beef juice (no fruit juice), - - - 38

These last two may be properly considered together, since there is no evidence that any treatment with drugs has an appreciable effect upon the disease. So many of the reported cases were treated with drugs alone without result before the correct diagnosis was made and other treatment instituted, that this belief is amply justified. Combining, therefore, divisions VI. and VII., and comparing the statements of the writers regarding the diet employed during treatment and that employed when the scurvy developed, we may make the following table based upon 58 cases.

Again the committee would state that no claim is made that the recovery was the result of the change, but that it quotes merely the statements of the correspondents to the effect that recovery took place after the change was made.

VI. AND VII.—RECOVERY FOLLOWING CHANGE IN DIET ALONE, WITH OR WITHOUT DRUGS. (NO FRUIT JUICE EMPLOYED).

Mellin's food to milk and beef juice,	-	-	-	-	2
" " to raw milk and beef juice,	-	-	-	-	1
" " to modified milk,	-	-	-	-	4
" " to modified milk and beef juice,	-	-	-	-	2
" " to diet and beef juice,	-	-	-	-	1
" " and sterilized milk to beef juice and broths,	-	-	-	-	1
" " and sterilized milk to sterilized milk and beef juice,	-	-	-	-	2

Lactated food to milk,	-	-	-	-	1
Reed & Carnrick's soluble food to milk, variously treated,	-	-	-	-	3
Malted milk to milk, variously treated,	-	-	-	-	38
Mellin's food to milk, variously treated,	-	-	-	-	21
Mellin's food and condensed milk to milk, variously treated,	-	-	-	-	19
Sterilized milk to fresh (probably always raw) milk,	-	-	-	-	34
Sterilized milk to pasteurized milk,	-	-	-	-	4
Pasteurized milk to "fresh" or "raw" milk,	-	-	-	-	9
Pasteurized milk to sterilized milk,	-	-	-	-	1
Raw milk to sterilized milk,	-	-	-	-	1
Breast milk to cow's milk, variously treated,	-	-	-	-	6

The conclusions to be drawn from this combined study of etiology and of treatment seem justifiable only to the following extent:

(1) That the development of the disease follows in each case the prolonged employment of some diet unsuitable to the individual child, and that often a change of diet which at first thought would seem to be unsuitable may be followed by prompt recovery.

(2) That in spite of this fact regarding individual cases, the combined report of collected cases makes it probable that in these there were certain forms of diet which were particularly prone to be followed by the development of scurvy. First in point of numbers here are to be mentioned the various proprietary foods.

(3) In fine, that in general the cases reported seem to indicate that the farther a food is removed in character from the natural food of a child the more likely its use is to be followed by the development of scurvy.

FATAL CASES.—Twenty-nine of the 379 cases are reported to have died. In 2 of these, death seems to have been remote from the attack of scurvy. Of the remaining 27 the causes as enumerated by the reporters are as follows:

Exhaustion, 6; cerebral hemorrhage, 3; diarrhœa, 2; bronchitis, 2; vomiting (?) 1; convulsions, 1; pneumonia, 4; malnutrition, 1; pulmonary hemorrhage, 1; ulcer of stomach, 1; syncope and nephritis, 1; doubtful, 4.

It is difficult to determine in how many of these the scurvy itself could be held responsible for the death; probably in few if any.

AUTOPSIES.—There have been handed in to the committee

the reports of 6 autopsies in all, some of them only partial. The salient points of each may be enumerated as follows:

Case of Dr. A. Caillé. Child of nine months, ill about three months. Autopsy showed hemorrhagic spots on the pericardium and surface of the liver; sub-periosteal hemorrhage of the long bones.

Case of Dr. L. E. Holt. Child of twelve months; ill for two months. Autopsy showed separation of the lower epiphysis from the shaft of the left femur; extensive sub-periosteal hemorrhage of the left femur; sub-pleural hemorrhages; broncho-pneumonia.

Case of Dr. L. E. Holt. Child of thirteen months; ill about two months. Autopsy showed sub-periosteal hemorrhage and separation of the lower epiphysis of the left femur; hemorrhages into the muscles of the left thigh, swellings about the opposite knee and both ankles; knee-joints normal; minute sub-pleural hemorrhages; well marked exudative nephritis; minute hemorrhages on the surface of the liver.

Case of W. P. Northrup. (The first autopsy in the United States). Child of eighteen months; ill about one month. Autopsy showed sub-periosteal hemorrhage of both tibiæ and both femora; detachment of the lower epiphysis of the left femur and maceration of lower end of shaft; broncho-pneumonia of left lung; no rachitic or syphilitic changes on microscopical examination.

Case of Dr. L. Starr. Child of thirteen months; ill for three months. Autopsy showed "right leg from knee to ankle stuffed with a puffy mass replacing normal tissue. Separation of both bones one inch above ankle."

Case of Dr. C. W. Townsend. Child of ten months; ill three to four weeks. Autopsy showed bloody serum in pleural cavity; perforating ulcer of the stomach; tubercular (?) process in peritoneum.

In conclusion the committee would thank publicly their correspondents who have sent their reports of cases and who are enumerated below. They are also greatly indebted to Dr. Wm. Schleif of Philadelphia for valuable aid in analyzing the circulars received and tabulating the results.

[Signed],

J. P. CROZER GRIFFITH, M.D., Philadelphia, }
 CHARLES G. JENNINGS, M.D., Detroit, } Committee.
 JOHN LOVETT MORSE, M.D., Boston. }

MINORITY REPORT.

1. From a study of this report and from due consideration of other known facts, scurvy appears to be a chronic ptomaine poisoning due to the absorption of toxins.

2. It follows the prolonged use of improper food and abnormal intestinal fermentation is a predisposing factor.

3. Sterilizing, pasteurizing, or cooking of milk food is not *per se* responsible for the scurvy condition.

4. A change of food and the administration of fruit juice and treatment of any underlying cause is the rational therapeutic procedure in scurvy.

(Signed) AUGUSTUS CAILLÉ, M.D.

DISCUSSION.

DR. CHRISTOPHER.—Does this report contain any definite conclusions as to the nature of scurvy? I heard Dr. Griffith give part of one. If it does, it seems to me we should strike them out, for we certainly cannot agree upon them. I will move, then, that all parts of the report giving conclusions be stricken out and all parts relating to the collection of data be retained and as such be published. (Seconded). Now, does it contain any conclusions? It certainly seems to me bad policy for this Society ever to adopt conclusions of any pathological matter. Even in so elaborately established a report as that of the Anti-toxin Committee, it is bad policy, and it looks like establishing scientific truths by legislation. The truths are valuable and should be published as far as possible.

DR. GRIFFITH.—I have had several letters, one just before I came from home, from men who wanted to know the conclusions of the committee. If this is to be of any value it must have some conclusions, because nobody except those deeply interested in scurvy, will read through the report and the tables. We are not to determine as a committee or a Society what produces scurvy, but we are analyzing reports of physicians. If 300 physicians say in so many cases these children were improperly fed and one physician says there was no improper food, the conclusion is before you. We do not say diet is the cause, but we say from the reports of these physicians, diet seemed to be the cause. As in the long German articles, the conclusions are placed at the end. We cannot get out of the fact that the conclusions are there. I think we ought to sum up here and there the facts that the report indicates.

DR. NORTHROP.—Why should we gather all these statistics and then put them out in a mass. It is like tabulating the work of a hospital without commenting upon what they have done.

would be very sorry to see this work set aside. It would be like a record that appeared not long ago of 500 cases of rheumatism without any comments.

DR. MORSE.—I feel that the conclusions that the committee has drawn up are entirely justified. If anything, they are much milder than the figures seem to indicate. But any further conclusions would call for some expression of opinion from the committee that must be based on their personal experience and it seemed best to leave that out. I feel very strongly that the paper should not be published without the conclusions.

DR. JENNINGS.—I sincerely regret that my opportunity for examining the report has not been sufficient to express an opinion upon it. From the examination I made I think that the conclusions of the committee are fully justified. Still, it would have pleased me better to have been present at the full meeting of the committee to hear the various expressions and perhaps my individual opinions might have been modified in that way. But as they stand now, the conclusions very nearly express my conclusions of the results of the investigation.

DR. BOOKER.—I went over the conclusions of the committee. There were some things I did not approve of, but we came by various modifications to something of an agreement and I am satisfied to stand by that agreement. The time we had for reviewing the report was very short, but I am willing to stand by the conclusions we came to.

DR. CAILLÉ.—I think that those conclusions are entirely safe and I do not personally object to them, but I would like to make a very short minority report based upon the cases I have collected. (See page 500).

DR. FORCHHEIMER.—Would it not be better to have the committee meet again and try to come to some conclusion, so that the report can be received as a whole? I move that the report be referred back to the committee with instructions to report to-morrow.

Dr. Christopher withdrew his motion and the motion made by Dr. Forchheimer was carried.

On the following day Dr. Griffith presented the revised report. Preceding this Dr. Rowland G. Freeman opened a discussion on the subject: "Shall all milk used for infant feeding be heated for the purpose of killing germs? If so, at what temperature, and how long shall this temperature be continued."

General discussion upon the report of the committee and the paper of Dr. Freeman then followed.

DR. BOOKER.—I have not had an opportunity to study the report required for a subject of so great importance to form an opinion upon it, and I beg to be excused from subscribing to it.

DR. BUCKINGHAM.—It appears to me that this report in all its bearings is as important a matter as can come before the Society at any time. It is important it should be settled right. It will be a serious thing to have it settled wrong. It seems to me that having heard the evidence offered to us and the reports made to us to-day, that there is just this to be said: if the evidence is accepted there is only one conclusion that can possibly be drawn and that is, the sterilization of milk has to do with the production of scurvy. When Dr. Caillé presented his minority report it seemed to me that what he did was to proffer the evidence that has come from his personal knowledge and the knowledge of his personal friends rather than the observations of people that he knows very little about. There are just two conclusions that can be drawn: Either sterilization of milk produces scurvy or collective investigations are not a safe way of getting information. For my part I am willing to accept either or both, and do accept both conclusions. But I hope very much we shall not insist upon the public accepting a lot of investigations until we are all united in accepting them. For my own part, I believe sterilization produces scurvy and the only reason it does not do it oftener is because of the imperfect way milk is sterilized. A great deal of milk masquerades under the name sterilized milk that is not sterilized.

DR. BOOKER.—When the sterilization of milk was introduced it was heralded by the medical profession as one of the most important advances in medicine. After ten years' experience in this method I am still of the same opinion, that it is one of the greatest advances that has been made in infant feeding. It was not claimed in the beginning that sterilization improved the digestion of milk. That part of the question has attracted so much attention that we have lost sight of the real object of sterilizing milk, that is, the prevention of sickness. The most important diseases which we have to deal with among infants are the digestive disorders in the summer time. The sterilization of the milk offers more advantages in checking or preventing those diseases than any other method which has yet been offered. Now has sterilization of milk so far done anything towards diminishing the summer diarrhœas of infants? We have not had reliable statistics to justify us in coming to conclusions. In the first place, sterilized milk has been used heretofore largely among the well-to-do, who are able to give the infants advantages which may of themselves be sufficient to avoid the disease. Again, the methods used for the sterilization of milk have not been sufficient. I believe that disease has been diminished by sterilization of milk and I believe the infantile mortality has been markedly reduced in New York, if I understood the President's address correctly, in the last few years since the sterilization of milk has been largely used there. Whatever the results have been, there is a brighter outlook in the future if we can continue along this line.

There is a great deal to be done in educating people in the handling of milk. If we can continue educating the people in this way, I believe a great deal will be done towards preventing disease in infants. It is possible that sterilization of milk may injure its nutritive properties to a slight extent. The chemical combinations in milk are held very loosely, and heating may be sufficient to destroy these relations. Heating may also coagulate some of the valuable proteids and to this extent the nutritive properties of milk may be somewhat injured. But the injury done by this is far outweighed by the greater advantage offered in preventing disease. As to the temperature at which milk should be sterilized, much depends upon the object of the sterilization and who is doing the sterilizing.

The ordinary methods of sterilizing milk do not sterilize the milk. They do not destroy certain harmful germs, germs which may not be harmful to the child if introduced into its body, but which are injurious to the milk. These germs are destroyed at a low temperature, such as the bacillus lactis aerogenes. Where the hope is only to destroy these germs, and it is understood that this is the object of the sterilization, the low temperature of pasteurization would be preferable, provided the pasteurization were conducted by a person who understood it or had the valuable apparatus presented by Dr. Freeman. Unfortunately, this apparatus is expensive and cannot be introduced where it is most needed. If we turn the sterilization over to the family I believe it is better to resort to sterilization than pasteurization. My own experience has been larger with sterilization than with pasteurization, and I do not believe there is a very great difference in the disturbance of the digestive qualities of the milk and the nutritive qualities by the one over the other. If the milk is to be kept for any time after its sterilization before it is used, as for journeys, it should be thoroughly sterilized, and that means a sterilization of three to six consecutive days at a high temperature for very many hours.

I particularly want to put myself on record that I do not believe the sterilization of milk causes the disturbances that have been claimed for it. I believe that in all the cases if we could get to the true knowledge of the previous management of the milk we would find it is that which has caused the trouble and not the manner of heating. It may be that certain idiosyncracies of the baby may be of such a nature that the sterilization of the milk will cause injury to the baby, but that may occur with any milk. When we analyze milk and find it normal as far as we can judge from the analysis, it may disagree with the infant. The sterilization, I believe, has no other influence in producing disease. I do not believe it produces scurvy. I believe that is due to the handling of the milk before and afterwards. Very few of us who have sent in reports have made examinations of the handling of the milk. I do not, and I believe very few have

done so. That is one reason I am not willing to subscribe to the report. If we could sift all these cases I believe we would find some condition in the milk, outside of sterilization, as we do in Mellin's food, which is mentioned in a number of cases under scurvy. It is very seldom Mellin's food is used as a food; it is not intended as a food but is more intended as a sugar for sweetening the milk. It is a valuable addition in some cases when it is used in that way. In all the answers I have received very few have said that they used Mellin's food alone; it is largely used with milk. If we could find out the true condition of the food before the scurvy was produced we would not find that the food bears such a relation to the disease. The whole subject is too complex and too little understood.

DR. WINTERS.—Two cases of scurvy which I have seen have a good deal of bearing, I think, on the discussion. One was a child nine months old that was brought to the dispensary too late to be reported to this committee. It was the fifth child, the other four in the family being absolutely healthy. The family history was excellent. This child had extensive changes under the periosteum which extended from the knee down to the ankle. It had the well known blue line beneath the two front teeth. The child had been fed exclusively for six months on sterilized milk. The other case was a baby five months old, brought to my office in consultation. The father and mother were healthy. This child was fed on Walker-Gorden milk and had never had anything else from its birth. That milk had been under sterilization for forty minutes. Here we have two typical cases of scurvy in which the family history has no bearing, one in which there has been four healthy children, both fed on proper food, and the scurvy, it seems to me, was due to the way in which the food was treated. The food in both cases was proper in composition and it had never caused the slightest digestive disturbances. In the case of the baby fed upon Walker-Gorden milk, the food was continued, but it was directed that it should be heated to 150° for ten minutes. The baby recovered. I have seen in all some two or three dozen cases of scurvy. The one case I spoke of was the only one that I have seen in dispensary practice, although I see thousands of children every year. My own impressions are that if the methods of feeding go on until we gradually meet the tenement people, we will also find scurvy in tenement practice. Every case of scurvy, except this one, I have seen in consultation. I have never used anything but a modification of food except in two cases, one a case which I saw with Dr. Reed, where beef juice and fruit juice were used, but the case was fatal.

DR. MORSE.—It seems to me that in approaching a collective investigation of any subject, the first thing necessary is to disabuse our minds of any previous ideas we may have held or failed

to hold. Then we should analyze our figures and study the result which they show, and we should not modify our result either because it does not agree with our previous points or because it seems to involve some issues which it is not our province to consider.

In regard to the sterilization of milk it seems to me that we must feel that the cooking of milk to any extent must modify albuminoids, proteid substances, and have some effect on the emulsion of fat. We must also admit that bacteria in milk do harm and for that reason we should heat milk to a certain extent. We have to meet two dangers, and in each individual case we must settle it according to our best judgment. One danger in connection with sterilized milk is that the public has forgotten that there is anything else in connection with baby's food except cooking it.

DR. JACOBI.—I can be very brief, inasmuch as I might have said something similar to what Dr. Morse has said just now. I arise to make a motion that the report and the minority report, and the remarks of Dr. Booker and this whole discussion be printed as it stands. We owe that to those who have done the work and we owe it to ourselves. We should not expect that we can solve the question forever. We must not expect that any report nor anything that any of us say must be accepted by the whole world. It is only a contribution to what has been known before. It would be a pity if the material which has been worked up should be lost. Whoever has spoken last upon this subject feels then that the subject is settled and that there is nothing further to be said about it. That has been so from the beginning of time and it is so now. What we say here and do here and our valuable report should be published, and the medical public who are going to read it will have something new at all events, either a confirmation of their original views or the opposite.

The Chair decided that the motion of Dr. Jacobi was not necessary, since the publication would be made according to the laws of the Society.

DR. ADAMS.—I am very much of the opinion expressed by Dr. Morse. We have a right to express our individual views. The investigation was entered into in all honesty and all deductions should be drawn from the figures presented by the public at large just as in the investigation of anti-toxin. We have a practice in the medical press of giving the public the benefit of individual opinions and this should be an independent investigation and not clouded by individual opinions. I have made observations in sterilizing milk, and I have my own opinions about scurvy, but I should be governed very much by the valuable report of this committee.

Now as to the discussion of milk. I, with very many mem-

bers of this Society, took up very early the high sterilization of milk, and was very soon convinced of its impracticability in the vast majority of cases. Then I resorted to the low sterilization. I have tried both methods in the most adverse circumstances, that is in a hot city where the temperature is often 80° for days at a time. I have done this under the most favorable circumstances with a good corps of good assistants and I have found one method has yielded entirely satisfactory results. While we have cardinal principles to govern us in feeding infants, we must study each individual case and adapt the methods accordingly. I have sterilized the milk in the Foundling Hospital and in the Children's Hospital, and then I pasteurized the milk in both of them, and I got bad results in both. Then I pasteurized at 150° in both and have secured the best milk possible and in this way I have had the best results. In the past two months I have not had any deaths among sixty children. In private practice, in those cases in which I could get them upon a supply of milk from a dairy under the medical supervision of the Society of the District of Columbia, I did not resort to either method but to my own modification of the milk by siphoning off the cream or the upper part of the milk. In this way I have not since January seen a case of gastro-enteric disease in my own practice. So I think our own experience should guide us rather than that we should lay down that all milk should be sterilized or all pasteurized.

DR. CAILLÉ.—I wish to say one word in Dr. Freeman's favor. I was asked by the council to sit as confrère in this matter, but I declined. I think we are getting a little hysterical in the matter of temperature and we will settle down to a solid basis after a while. The antiseptic principle applied to infant food is one of the greatest advanced in the last half of this century. If the opinion should go out from this Society that sterilization is bad practice, it would be a large retrograde step. It would be all right if it were possible to have absolutely clean milk from the time it is received until it is consumed, but since this is impossible, I prefer the sterilizing process rather than pasteurization, because pasteurization is a double process, a heating and a cooling process, and is a complicated thing for the common people to do. For that reason I prefer the temperature of boiling water. In reply to what Dr. Buckingham has said I will only say that my conclusions in the scurvy discussion are based upon the study of all the 370 odd cases, and Dr. Buckingham's conclusions are not based upon those cases. He has simply heard the report read and has not studied it as I have. Therefore, I think he is the bolder man of the two in formulating his conclusions.

DR. JENNINGS.—I have nothing further to add. Dr. Morse expressed my views even better than I did, and I stand by that expression.

DR. GRIFFITH.—I want to say that Dr. Morse has expressed my views. We are disposed to reflect upon the observers we do not know and say that we do not know anything about them; we do not know whether their milk was properly prepared, etc. I have read through every report sent me, with the exception of the few last ones, which included principally Dr. Holt's batch which I thought it hardly worth while to review. You will be surprised to hear with what care those cases are reported by men we do not know. We say here "sterilization"; they say "sterilized at 212° for so long." It was impossible in the report to make all these classifications. At the same time the committee has taken particular pains not to vouch for the statements made. We do not know how many are accurate, of course, and so we only took the figures received, added them up and gave you the results. That only expresses the tabulation of these cases. In regard to Dr. Freeman's paper, I would like to express my own custom and belief about sterilization and pasteurization of milk. I do not believe that sterilization does the harm usually attributed to it. It has been the custom among many people for a long time to so-called scald the milk, which raised it to near the temperature of boiling water. I think we do find comparatively little harm from this. At the same time we should get as near as possible the mother's milk. The sterilized or pasteurized milk is simply a lesser evil. Any condition of this kind is an evil and the only question is whether the evil of omitting it is not greater than the evil of doing it. Certainly in my mind it is better to boil the milk thoroughly and long, if necessary, to insure clean milk. If you cannot do that I would prefer pasteurization, or better than that, raw milk.

DR. HOLT.—Most of us believe that at times pasteurization of the milk is absolutely necessary, especially among certain people at certain times; but here is a thing, from the report that may be dangerous and let us admit that. I have seen cases precisely like those reported in which there seemed to be no question about the preparation of the food, and the change from boiled milk or milk which was raw was the only step toward recovery. In my early cases I gave no fruit juice but only changed the food. It seems to me there are many things done in private practice that cannot be done outside. But that there is danger in the prolonged use of sterilized milk, it seems to me, is something we cannot escape if we believe these men have told the truth. It is a thing that will occur at times, and when a baby gets sore gums and sore legs we will know what is wrong.

DR. BOOKER.—I would like to say that I believe in sterilization of the milk as a preventive measure and not as a food for the whole year. The proper time for using it is from June to October. In the cooler seasons, when we have tolerably pure milk, the raw milk is the best.

DR. FREEMAN.—Dr. Booker referred to the difficulty of pasteurizing in poor practice where you cannot have the proper apparatus. It is perfectly practicable to pasteurize at 80° C. without any apparatus at all, if we will exert a little care, the milk being put on the stove and watched until a film forms on it. That is not true of diluted milk but of pure milk. That requires about fifteen or twenty minutes as a rule. It gives you some error perhaps in the way of over-heating rather than under-heating. In regard to Dr. Caillé's remark that one of the disadvantages is that you have to keep all milk cool afterwards, I think that is not true. In sterilization where pressure was used and the sterilization continued about twenty minutes, we found a growth of bacteria within a day.

ACTION OF THE SOCIETY.

On motion, the majority report was adopted by a vote of 18 to 1.
